

STRUCTURE SCHEME OF CREATION OF A LARGE DATABASE IN THE PROCESS OF CONVERGENCE OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES

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Annotation: In this article, the importance and relevance of creating a large database in the process of convergence of educational services, as well as their theoretical and practical aspects, are highlighted, and opinions are expressed on this topic. Within the framework of the approach based on the economic directions of the knowledge economy, specific theoretical information is given on the formation of competencies for the purpose of training future specialists in the economic direction.

Key words: Secondary education, higher education, school education, convergence, knowledge economy, pedagogical skills, database, convergence process, educational services.

In the process of convergence of educational services, a large database is definitely formed. The development and modernization of educational services depends on the development of information technologies as the main factors of education. There is a need to develop the information environment of education, to introduce new modules of education, to modernize information transmission channels.

During the formation of these processes, they face the problem of shortage of specialists in the professions who can teach about Digital technologies, artificial intelligence, computer techniques and robotics at various levels. The implementation of various information systems in education allows to solve the issues of completeness, reliability and confidentiality of the received information. However, there is very little research on the implementation and use of convergence in education.

During the research, methods of logical analysis based on theoretical materials of the convergence of the knowledge economy in the educational system, presented in scientific literature, were used. Methods and approaches such as induction and deduction, space and time, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis were used in the analysis of available data.

According to scientists, digital development should be at the center of human learning. Creativity and critical thinking are important in human development today. Accordingly, the digital concept is divided into 3 types: knowledge, skill and attitude approximation. Modern education should organize

education using new innovations and technologies. Newly produced technologies should serve to improve the quality of education and organize educational processes.

Figure 1. A structural diagram of the creation of a large database in the process of convergence of educational services

Figure 1 shows that the experimenter actively communicates with the MBBT. Before communicating with the workstations, information about the monitored control indicators and its final production in the network is used. If the indicator is greater than one, demand is greater than supply, if less than one, the opposite is true. The control indicators are analyzed at the position of the degree that is acceptable by the experimenter. If they need to change, the operator can change this or that control parameter. Blocks define new adjustable pointers.

As soon as the operator concludes that a satisfactory balance has been reached, he transfers the system to the workstations.

Thus, the provision of the information model, through the human-machine simulation system, allows to create an information base that provides the best ratio of information use to the industrial structure and to ensure their security.

Creation of information supply of educational system convergence control parameters, evaluation of intermediate decisions and selection of final decisions is imposed on the information technology center ATM operator, most of the possible solution options are solved in the database management system (MBBT).

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